

Interdisciplinary strategies to assess the relationship between exposure to complex chemical mixtures and thyroid hormone system disruption

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Abstract

The possible risk that exposure to chemicals leads to disruption of the thyroid hormone (TH) system in humans and animals can be assessed through biomonitoring of chemicals for which TH system disruption has been demonstrated in animal studies. In addition, epidemiological studies may establish a relationship between exposure to chemicals and adverse outcomes on the thyroid hormone system. However, such studies are often limited to single chemicals or classes of chemicals, and do not account for the complex mixtures to which humans and animals are exposed, consisting of multiple chemicals that in combination may affect similar or different endpoints in the TH system. The use of *in vivo*, and *in vitro* studies using complex extracts coming from real-life samples is necessary to unravel the specific effects that chemical mixtures inflict on the TH system. In addition, approaches such as effect-directed analysis that combine bioassays with integrated chemical analysis allow the identification of mixture risk drivers avoiding the loss of chemicals due to excessive sample processing.

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Keywords

Effect directed analysis, Mixtures, Real-life samples, Thyroid hormone system-disrupting chemicals.

1. Introduction

The thyroid hormone (TH) system is responsible for controlling growth and development of the foetus and during childhood, as well as regulating physiological,

metabolic, and reproductive functions in adulthood. For instance, normal brain development requires balanced TH levels not only during gestational phases but also throughout postnatal maturation [1,2]. In addition, THs also play a significant role in regulating body temperature, energy expenditure, metabolism, and immune responses. The TH system can be disrupted during TH synthesis, distribution, transmembrane transport, or metabolism, and during TH action on specific targets [2,3]. In the last decades, the disruption of the TH system by exogenous chemicals has been widely studied [4,5]. *In vivo* studies evaluating the effects of chemicals in animal models [6], *in vitro* models used to unravel the chemical potency of endocrine-disrupting chemicals (EDC) in specific cell lines or protein-based assays [7–9], *in silico* calculations to model ligand binding sites [7,10] or to reveal underlying interaction mechanisms [8], are only a few examples of how the scientific community has been generating significant data to understand the complexity of TH system disruptors and their mechanisms of action. However, these experimental and computational approaches are mostly focused on the action of single chemicals, or specific groups of chemicals such as per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs), polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), organophosphorus flame retardants, phthalates, and bisphenols.

Since humans, domestic and feral animals are exposed to mixtures of chemicals from different sources (environment, food and other consumer goods, cleaning products, house dust, etc.) and via different routes simultaneously, mixture effects like additivity, synergism, or antagonism can be overlooked when doing chemical risk assessment. Therefore, this review will focus on the latest advances in the research of TH system disruption by complex mixtures from different sources with a focus on biota samples collected from organisms including humans exposed to environmental chemicals, such as serum, breast milk, or placenta.

2. Biomonitoring and exposure studies of TH system disrupting chemicals in humans, domestic animals, and wildlife

Human biomonitoring data are very relevant for chemical risk assessment. Not only because it provides

exposure data of well-classified chemicals of concern, but also because it allows to explore new potential exposure pathways for emerging substances. Some countries and regions have been extensively monitoring chemical substances of concern for the past 30 years [11–16]. In addition, the Human Biomonitoring 4 the European Union (HBM4EU) project [17] has combined and harmonized human biomonitoring data to align all biomonitoring initiatives in Europe, not only for general chemical substances of concern [18], but also for EDCs specifically [19–21].

Biomonitoring and exposure studies of EDCs have increased considerably in the last few years. For example, hair samples have been postulated to be a good source to assess long-term exposure to bisphenols and phthalates [22]. Hand wipes have been used to study dermal exposure to chlorinated organophosphorus flame retardants in adults from a typical e-waste dismantling area [23]. In this study, flame-retardant levels in hand wipes correlated with levels detected in serum and urine samples, and significant exposure differences were found depending on the specific work activity. Along the same lines, a study performed in the Netherlands monitored PBDEs and organophosphorus flame retardants in house dust and body wipes to estimate the chemical exposure in toddlers [24]. This study evidenced significant exposure differences between gender, and age of Dutch toddlers, and directly correlated flame-retardant concentration patterns between the contaminated source (dust) and the main dermal absorption site (toddler's hands). The highest concentration of flame retardants was detected on the hand wipes of the boys, and this concentration decreased with age. Moreover, pet cats have been demonstrated to be a good exposure model for indoor exposure to brominated flame retardants via dust and food [25]. The same Swedish research group highlighted the fact that higher exposure to indoor organic chemicals could be related to feline hyperthyroidism, and concluded that cats may act as sentinels for human exposure to indoor contaminants [26]. Biomonitoring of EDCs is not only important for humans and domesticated animals. Wildlife is often exposed to these chemicals as well, threatening the fauna and biodiversity of certain areas. Since polar bears are exposed to the highest levels of persistent organic pollutants in the Arctic due to bioaccumulation, and their TH system has an important role in thermoregulation, metabolism, and reproduction, many studies have focused on TH system-disrupting chemicals in this species [27]. Two studies by Bytingsvik et al. compared plasma levels of PCBs, hydroxylated PCBs, and PFASs in polar bear mothers and their cubs, collected in 1998 and in 2008 [28,29]. A general reduction of PCBs and sulfonated PFASs in blood was seen in both mothers and cubs in 2008 compared to 1998. However, an increase in carboxylated PFASs could be detected in the course of these 10 years. These studies demonstrated the efficacy

of emission reductions of some chemicals like perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), and demonstrated the need to investigate lesser-known chemicals, like carboxylated PFASs, in order to adequately regulate the use of new chemicals. In conclusion, biomonitoring and exposure studies demonstrate that humans, pets, and wildlife are exposed to very complex mixtures of potential TH system-disrupting chemicals. However, they cannot demonstrate the relationship between exposure to such chemicals and TH system disruption as epidemiological studies can.

3. Effects of TH system-disrupting chemical mixtures in humans and animals

The number of epidemiological studies that relate exposure to chemical classes such as PBDEs, PFASs, or phthalates to TH system disruption is increasing continuously. Meta-analyses confirming correlations between exposures and disrupting effects on TH homeostasis in these epidemiological studies are also increasing at a similar pace. On the other hand, the results of such meta-analyses can be quite ambiguous. For instance, a very recent meta-analysis by Zhang et al. [30] collected sufficient evidence to demonstrate that PFOS and PFOA are associated with increased thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) during the first 6 months of pregnancy, while in another meta-analysis, Kim et al. [31] could not find any associations between PFASs and TSH in pregnant women. Both meta-analyses did not find any correlation between PFAS exposure and circulating levels of total thyroxine (TT4), total triiodothyronine (TT3), free T4 (FT4), and free T3 (FT3) in pregnant women, although Zhang et al. found some associations in subgroup analyses, mainly indicating increased FT4 levels with increasing PFOS/PFOA in European studies. Other meta-analyses that attempted to correlate TH levels in neonates with prenatal exposure to toxicants like PCBs and/or phthalates [32], children, adults, and pregnant women [33] also showed disparate results. There are many reasons that could explain these differences. Besides the intrinsic limitations of the meta-analyses themselves (number of studies available or considered, selection criteria, outliers' exclusion, or other adjustment factors), the sample size of the epidemiological studies included plays a very important role in the statistical analysis. Increasing the number of participants in cohorts would definitely increase the statistical power, resulting in more robust correlations. Moreover, the chemical co-exposures that take place in real life and their effects are often not taken into account, and the simultaneous effect of different chemical classes might be dismissed.

Different associations between early pregnancy exposure to PFAS and the homeostasis of the maternal TH system were also found in the SELMA cohort. While higher exposure to most of the studied PFAS was

associated with higher FT4, no associations were found between exposure to these chemicals and FT3, TSH, or TSH/FT4 ratios in maternal serum [34]. Furthermore, individual and mixture effects have also been evaluated using multiple statistical regression models in a mother-child prospective study to associate TH system disruption with the exposure to classes of EDCs like PFASs, considering PCBs and PBDEs as potential covariates [35]. However, the results of this study did not show any strong associations between maternal serum PFASs concentrations in pregnancy and THs in maternal and cord sera, maybe because the serum sampling time was too early in pregnancy (week 6) or because the study design neglected other confounders (i.e., only 4 PFASs were considered). In fact, another mixture modelling study with 6 PFASs (including the 4 used in the previous model) found negative associations between maternal plasma levels (average 9.6 weeks gestation) of these chemicals as a mixture and the maternal FT4 and neonatal T4 in male newborns [36]. In another study, however, TH serum levels in newborns were positively correlated to late pregnancy and prenatal PFAS exposure determined as PFAS levels in umbilical cord blood [37]. Such inconsistencies between studies may be attributed to the differences in study design (PFASs mixtures, or single chemical exposure), sample type (maternal serum vs cord blood), and (regional) differences in exposure levels. In pet cats, increase in serum TT4 levels was correlated to an increase of one specific PFAS (PFNA) present in house dust [38]. Negative correlations were found between exposure to organohalogen mixtures and TH levels in the serum of these house pets [39]. In wild fish, disruption of the TH system and immune homeostasis has been associated with lifelong exposures coming from contaminated lakes [40], which is not only relevant for the regional ecosystem, but also for potential effects in humans by exposure to EDCs through the diet. The application of machine learning to these kinds of large data sets from various studies has been suggested as a logical approach for addressing multi-exposure events in the future to allow the prediction of chemical mixture bioavailability and toxicity based on previous exposure data [41]. To the best of our knowledge, controlled *in vivo* studies that assess TH system disruption by chemical mixtures are scarce, although such studies are relevant as demonstrated by Wade et al. [42], Crofton et al. [43], and Conley et al. [44]. These studies have shown the disruption of the TH system in rats after exposure to reconstituted complex chemical mixtures reflecting environmental exposure levels.

Besides mixture model and human or animal studies, the potency of EDC mixtures to interfere with TH homeostasis has also been assessed in small-scale *in vivo* or *in vitro* bioassays for reconstituted mixtures mimicking chemical compositions from house dust, human serum [45] and amniotic fluid [46], and from

extracts of different water sources [47]. In addition, *in vitro* bioassays were used to assess the TH system disrupting potency of complex mixtures present in extracts of polar bear serum [48], house dust [49], and human placenta [50]. However, the effects observed in the *in vitro* bioassays cannot be directly translated to an adverse outcome in real-life. To do so, the derivation of effect-based trigger (EBT) values has been proposed in environmental effect-based risk assessment as a suitable approach to differentiate between acceptable and unacceptable chemical water quality [51,52]. Within the EU funded project PANORAMIX [53], this approach will be taken forward by deriving bioassay-specific EBT values that distinguish acceptable bioassay responses to cord blood samples from bioassay responses of concern for the health of newborns. This innovative approach will grant the development of mechanism-based EBT values for chemical mixtures targeting the disruption of the endocrine system and neurotoxicity pathways. In addition, a more concise chemical identification will be pursued in case the EBTs of such bioassays increase to concerning levels [53].

4. Identification of TH system-disrupting chemicals in complex mixtures

Even though the use of realistic, complex samples and extracts is a great advantage to evaluate mixture effects in a more pragmatic way, it is essential to identify key components of those mixtures responsible for the observed effects, and unravel their potential role in complex real-life situations. Scientific and technical developments of the past years such as high-throughput effect-directed analysis (EDA) and suspect screening of complex real-life mixtures have proven to be essential tools to reach this goal. For example, the unknown contaminants contributing to the transthyretin (TTR)-binding activity in polar bear serum [48] were further investigated by EDA showing that along with mono-hydroxylated PCB metabolites, di-hydroxylated PCB metabolites contributed to this activity as well [54]. A very similar approach was used on sediment samples, which can be considered as the reservoir of exposure for the aquatic environment [55]. Both investigations concluded that extensive and more sensitive identification of the chemicals present in the sample is fundamental to elucidate which mixture components contribute to the TTR-binding activity of the extract. Another EDA study identified aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR) agonists in the polar fractions of extracts of livers of black-tailed gulls [56]. Although this research was not directly investigating the disruption of the TH system, the potential cross-talk between the signalling pathways of the AhR and the nuclear TH receptor makes all the 7 identified agonists potential candidates for inclusion in specific suspect lists for the identification of TH system-disrupting chemicals. Recently, our research group has validated a high-throughput EDA approach, bringing together the latest technology of fractionation

and chemical identification that combines multiple bioassays. In this specific case, the TTR-binding assay and an antibiotics bioassay [57]. In principle, this approach can be applied to any type of miniaturized *in vivo* or *in vitro* bioassay [58]. This integration of chemical and toxicological assessments for the identification of mixture risk drivers is currently being explored for various samples and implemented for the assessment of several developmental pathways, including the TH system [53,58].

Despite the fast development over the last years in analytical technology, bioassay testing, and identification approaches, EDA studies still face several challenges. In most cases, for instance, compounds associated with specific biological activities cannot explain the entire mixture effect of the extract, indicating that some unidentified chemicals might play a role in TH system disruption. To avoid that part of the unexplained bioassay response is due to matrix effects from the extract on the measured activity or read-out, sample preparation approaches and the subsequent bioassays should be carefully considered, analysed, and validated for each sample type. In addition, the current methods for extraction, fractionation and high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) analysis are tailored towards organic chemicals of a certain range of polarity.

For example, the extraction methods applied often cover only a limited hydrophobicity range, which implies that very polar compounds will be overlooked. Moreover, bioassay interferences with endogenous elements of the sample can force the sample extraction to be distorted as well. For instance, a clean-up step for endogenous hormones may be required to assess androgen/estrogen agonistic or antagonistic effects of xenobiotics in biological samples. This clean-up, however, may also eliminate chemicals of interest that could contribute to TH system disruption, such as bisphenol A [59]. In conclusion, assessments of chemical mixtures mimicking real-life samples are often biased towards substances belonging to a limited chemical space.

5. Conclusions

The research advances concerning the effects of chemical mixtures on the TH system in the last years are evident (Figure 1). Biomonitoring studies demonstrate that humans and other animals are exposed to EDCs from various sources in the living environment that end up in systemic circulation. However, epidemiological mixture modelling studies and cohort analysis present substantial uncertainties when trying to find a causal relationship between chemical mixtures and their role in the TH system disruption. Experimental *in vivo* and *in vitro* approaches using reconstituted mixtures or

Figure 1

Strategies currently used to monitor and assess the effect of real-life chemical mixtures acting as thyroid hormone (TH) system disruptors in humans, domestic animals, and wildlife.

complex extracts have demonstrated their added value, but there is the need for EBTs for the bioassay results to link these responses to a possible concern for adverse outcomes in real-life. In addition, the chemical analyses cannot yet fully explain the overall effects observed in the sample or extract. To diminish some of these uncertainties more harmonized methodologies for sample extraction, chemical analysis, and assessment of the biological effects of chemicals of concern are needed. The combination of bioassays with integrated chemical analysis approaches that is provided by EDA will allow the scientific community to identify chemicals that are mixture risk drivers within complex samples without the need for excessive sample processing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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References

Papers of particular interest, published within the period of review, have been highlighted as:

- * of special interest
- ** of outstanding interest

1. Boas M, Feldt-Rasmussen U, Skakkebaek NE, Main KM: **Environmental chemicals and thyroid function**. *Eur J Endocrinol* 2006, **154**:599–611.
 2. Ghassabian A, Trasande L: **Disruption in thyroid signaling pathway: a mechanism for the effect of endocrine-disrupting chemicals on child neurodevelopment**. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)* 2018, **9**:204.
 3. Jugan ML, Levi Y, Blondeau JP: **Endocrine disruptors and thyroid hormone physiology**. *Biochem Pharmacol* 2010, **79**:939–947.
 4. Köhrle J, Frädrich C: **Thyroid hormone system disrupting chemicals**. *Best Pract Res Clin Endocrinol Metabol* 2021, **35**:101562.
- This review focuses on the most recent experimental animal studies and epidemiological studies done to assess thyroid hormone disrupting chemicals resulting in practice points and a research agenda for the future.
5. Sokal A, Jarmakiewicz-Czaja S, Tabarkiewicz J, Filip R: **Dietary intake of endocrine disrupting substances presents in environment and their impact on thyroid function**. *Nutrients* 2021, **13**:867.
 6. Ramhoj L, Hass U, Gilbert ME, Wood C, Svingen T, Usai D, Vinggaard AM, Mandrup K, Axelstad M: **Evaluating thyroid hormone disruption: investigations of long-term neurodevelopmental effects in rats after perinatal exposure to perfluorohexane sulfonate (PFHxS)**. *Sci Rep* 2020, **10**:2672.
 7. Cotrina EY, Oliveira A, Llop J, Quintana J, Biarnes X, Cardoso I, Diaz-Cruz MS, Arsequell G: **Binding of common organic UV-filters to the thyroid hormone transport protein transthyretin using in vitro and in silico studies: potential implications in health**. *Environ Res* 2022, **217**:114836.
 8. Li J, Xu Y, Li N, Zuo R, Zhai Y, Chen H: **Thyroid hormone disruption by organophosphate esters is mediated by nuclear/membrane thyroid hormone receptors: in vitro, in vivo, and in silico studies**. *Environ Sci Technol* 2022, **56**:4241–4250.
 9. Carvalho DJ, Kip AM, Romitti M, Nazzari M, Tegel A, Stich M, Krause C, Caiment F, Costagliola S, Moroni L: **Thyroid-on-a-chip: an organoid platform for in vitro assessment of endocrine disruption**. *Adv Healthcare Materials* 2022: 2201555.
 10. Dharpure R, Pramanik S, Pradhan A. *In Silico analysis decodes transthyretin (TTR) binding and thyroid disrupting effects of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS)*, *Arch Toxicol*, 2022.
 11. Koch HM, Ruther M, Schutze A, Conrad A, Palmke C, Apel P, Bruning T, Kolossa-Gehring M: **Phthalate metabolites in 24-h urine samples of the German Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB) from 1998 to 2015 and a comparison with US NHANES data from 1999 to 2012**. *Int J Hyg Environ Health* 2017, **220**(2 Pt A):130–141.
 12. Reynders H, Colles A, Morrens B, Mampaey M, Coertjens D, Koppen G, Schoeters G, Loots I, Chovanova H, Winderickx W, Van Campenhout K: **The added value of a surveillance human biomonitoring program: the case of FLEHS in Flanders (Belgium)**. *Int J Hyg Environ Health* 2017, **220**(2 Pt A):46–54.
 13. Wang Y, Zhu H, Kannan K: **A review of biomonitoring of phthalate exposures**. *Toxics* 2019, **7**.
 14. Dereumeaux C, Fillol C, Charles MA, Denys S: **The French human biomonitoring program: first lessons from the perinatal component and future needs**. *Int J Hyg Environ Health* 2017, **220**(2 Pt A):64–70.
 15. Correia-Sa L, Kasper-Sonnenberg M, Schutze A, Palmke C, Norberto S, Calhau C, Domingues VF, Koch HM: **Exposure assessment to bisphenol A (BPA) in Portuguese children by human biomonitoring**. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int* 2017, **24**:27502–27514.
 16. Urbancova K, Dvorakova D, Gramblicka T, Sram RJ, Hajslova J, Pulkrabova J: **Comparison of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon metabolite concentrations in urine of mothers and their newborns**. *Sci Total Environ* 2020, **723**:138116.
 17. HBM4EU Project. <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/>.
 18. Gilles L, Govarts E, Rambaud L, Vogel N, Castano A, López ME, Martin LR, Koppen G, Remy S, Vrijheid M: **HBM4EU combines and harmonises human biomonitoring data across the EU, building on existing capacity—The HBM4EU survey**. *Int J Hyg Environ Health* 2021, **237**:113809.
 19. Johansson HK, Boberg J, Dybdahl M, Axelstad M, Vinggaard AM: **Chemical risk assessment based on in vitro and human biomonitoring data: a case study on thyroid toxicants**. *Current Opinion in Toxicology* 2019, **15**:8–17.
 20. Demeneix BA: **Evidence for prenatal exposure to thyroid disruptors and adverse effects on brain development**. *Eur Thyroid J* 2019, **8**:283–292.
 21. Richterová D, Govarts E, Fábelová L, Rausová K, Martin LR, Gilles L, Remy S, Colles A, Rambaud L, Riou M: **PFAS levels and determinants of variability in exposure in European teenagers—Results from the HBM4EU aligned studies (2014–2021)**. *Int J Hyg Environ Health* 2023, **247**:114057.
 22. Katsikantami I, Tzatzarakis MN, Karzi V, Stavroulaki A, Xezonaki P, Vakonaki E, Alegakis AK, Sifakis S, Rizos AK, Tsatsakis AM: **Biomonitoring of bisphenols A and S and phthalate metabolites in hair from pregnant women in Crete**. *Sci Total Environ* 2020, **712**:135651.
 23. Tang J, Ma S, Hu X, Lin M, Li G, Yu Y, An T: **Handwipes as indicators to assess organophosphate flame retardants exposure and thyroid hormone effects in e-waste dismantlers**. *J Hazard Mater* 2023, **443**(Pt B):130248.

24. Sugeng EJ, Leonards PE, van de Bor M: **Brominated and organophosphorus flame retardants in body wipes and house dust, and an estimation of house dust hand-loadings in Dutch toddlers.** *Environ Res* 2017, **158**:789–797.
25. Norrgran Engdahl J, Bignert A, Jones B, Athanassiadis I, Bergman A, Weiss JM: **Cats' internal exposure to selected brominated flame retardants and organochlorines correlated to house dust and cat food.** *Environ Sci Technol* 2017, **51**:3012–3020.
26. Weiss J, Jones B: **Using cats as sentinels for human indoor exposure to organic contaminants and potential effects on the thyroid hormone system.** *Pets as Sentinels, Forecasters and Promoters of Human Health* 2020:123–139. Springer.
27. Routti H, Atwood TC, Bechshoft T, Boltunov A, Ciesielski TM, Desforjes J-P, Dietz R, Gabrielsen GW, Jenssen BM, Letcher RJ: **State of knowledge on current exposure, fate and potential health effects of contaminants in polar bears from the circumpolar Arctic.** *Sci Total Environ* 2019, **664**:1063–1083.
28. Bytingsvik J, Lie E, Aars J, Derocher AE, Wiig Ø, Jenssen BM: **PCBs and OH-PCBs in polar bear mother–cub pairs: a comparative study based on plasma levels in 1998 and 2008.** *Sci Total Environ* 2012, **417**:117–128.
29. Bytingsvik J, van Leeuwen SP, Hamers T, Swart K, Aars J, Lie E, Nilsen EME, Wiig Ø, Derocher AE, Jenssen BM: **Perfluoroalkyl substances in polar bear mother–cub pairs: a comparative study based on plasma levels from 1998 and 2008.** *Environ Int* 2012, **49**:92–99.
30. Zhang L, Liang J, Gao A: **Contact to perfluoroalkyl substances and thyroid health effects: a meta-analysis directing on pregnancy.** *Chemosphere* 2023:137748.
31. Kim MJ, Moon S, Oh B-C, Jung D, Ji K, Choi K, Park YJ: **Association between perfluoroalkyl substances exposure and thyroid function in adults: a meta-analysis.** *PLoS One* 2018, **13**, e0197244.
32. Sun M, Cao X, Wu Y, Shen L, Wei G: **Prenatal exposure to endocrine-disrupting chemicals and thyroid function in neonates: a systematic review and meta-analysis.** *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf* 2022, **231**:113215.
33. Kim MJ, Moon S, Oh B-C, Jung D, Choi K, Park YJ: **Association between diethylhexyl phthalate exposure and thyroid function: a meta-analysis.** *Thyroid* 2019, **29**:183–192.
34. Derakhshan A, Kortenkamp A, Shu H, Broeren MAC, Lindh CH, Peeters RP, Bornehag CG, Demeneix B, Korevaar TIM: **Association of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances with thyroid homeostasis during pregnancy in the SELMA study.** *Environ Int* 2022, **167**:107420.
35. Lebeaux RM, Doherty BT, Gallagher LG, Zoeller RT, Hoofnagle AN, Calafat AM, Karagas MR, Yolton K, Chen A, Lanphear BP, Braun JM, Romano ME: **Maternal serum perfluoroalkyl substance mixtures and thyroid hormone concentrations in maternal and cord sera: the HOME Study.** *Environ Res* 2020, **185**:109395.
36. Preston EV, Webster TF, Claus Henn B, McClean MD, Gennings C, Oken E, Rifas-Shiman SL, Pearce EN, Calafat AM, Fleisch AF, Sagiv SK: **Prenatal exposure to per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances and maternal and neonatal thyroid function in the Project Viva Cohort: a mixtures approach.** *Environ Int* 2020, **139**:105728.
37. Guo J, Zhang J, Wang Z, Zhang L, Qi X, Zhang Y, Chang X, Wu C, Zhou Z: **Umbilical cord serum perfluoroalkyl substance mixtures in relation to thyroid function of newborns: findings from Sheyang Mini Birth Cohort Study.** *Chemosphere* 2021, **273**:129664.
38. Weiss JM, Jones B, Koekkoek J, Bignert A, Lamoree MH: **Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) in Swedish household dust and exposure of pet cats.** *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int* 2021, **28**:39001–39013.
39. Nomiya K, Yamamoto Y, Eguchi A, Nishikawa H, Mizukawa H, Yokoyama N, Ichii O, Takiguchi M, Nakayama SM, Ikenaka Y: **Health impact assessment of pet cats caused by organohalogen contaminants by serum metabolomics and thyroid hormone analysis.** *Science of The Total Environment*; 2022:156490.
40. Birgersson L, Jouve J, Jönsson E, Asker N, Andreasson F, Golovko O, Ahrens L, Sturve J: **Thyroid function and immune status in perch (*Perca fluviatilis*) from lakes contaminated with PFASs or PCBs.** *Ecotoxicol Environ Saf* 2021, **222**:112495.
41. Cipullo S, Snapir B, Prpich G, Campo P, Coulon F: **Prediction of bioavailability and toxicity of complex chemical mixtures through machine learning models.** *Chemosphere* 2019, **215**:388–395.
42. Wade MG, Parent S, Finnson KW, Foster W, Younglai E, McMahon A, Cyr DG, Hughes C: **Thyroid toxicity due to subchronic exposure to a complex mixture of 16 organochlorines, lead, and cadmium.** *Toxicol Sci* 2002, **67**:207–218.
43. Crofton KM, Craft ES, Hedge JM, Gennings C, Simmons JE, Carchman RA, Carter Jr WH, DeVito MJ: **Thyroid-hormone-disrupting chemicals: evidence for dose-dependent additivity or synergism.** *Environ Health Perspect* 2005, **113**:1549–1554.
44. Conley JM, Lambright CS, Evans N, Medlock-Kakaley E, Dixon A, Hill D, McCord J, Strynar MJ, Ford J, Gray Jr LE: **Cumulative maternal and neonatal effects of combined exposure to a mixture of perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (PFOS) during pregnancy in the Sprague-Dawley rat.** *Environ Int* 2022, **170**:107631.
45. Hamers T, Kortenkamp A, Scholze M, Molenaar D, Ceniñ PH, Weiss JM: **Transthyretin-binding activity of complex mixtures representing the composition of thyroid-hormone disrupting contaminants in house dust and human serum.** *Environ Health Perspect* 2020, **128**:17015.
- Authors determine the Transthyretin-Binding potency in reconstituted mixtures mimicking median concentrations of chemicals in house dust, maternal serum, or infant serum. Experimental dissociation constants were used to estimate 1.5% inhibition levels of T4-TTR binding in human infant blood.
46. Fini J-B, Mughal BB, Le Mével S, Leemans M, Lettmann M, Spiranzlova P, Affaticati P, Jenett A, Demeneix BA: **Human amniotic fluid contaminants alter thyroid hormone signalling and early brain development in *Xenopus* embryos.** *Sci Rep* 2017, **7**:1–12.
47. Leusch FDL, Aneck-Hahn NH, Cavanagh JE, Du Pasquier D, Hamers T, Hebert A, Neale PA, Scheurer M, Simmons SO, Schriks M: **Comparison of in vitro and in vivo bioassays to measure thyroid hormone disrupting activity in water extracts.** *Chemosphere* 2018, **191**:868–875.
48. Bytingsvik J, Simon E, Leonards PE, Lamoree M, Lie E, Aars J, Derocher AE, Wiig Ø, Jenssen BM, Hamers T: **Transthyretin-binding activity of contaminants in blood from polar bear (*Ursus maritimus*) cubs.** *Environ Sci Technol* 2013, **47**:4778–4786.
49. Kollitz EM, Kassotis CD, Hoffman K, Ferguson PL, Sosa JA, Stapleton HM: **Chemical mixtures isolated from house dust disrupt thyroid receptor β signaling.** *Environ Sci Technol* 2018, **52**:11857–11864.
50. Rodríguez-Carrillo A, Rosenmai AK, Mustieles V, Couderq S, Fini J-B, Vela-Soria F, Molina-Molina JM, Ferrando-Marco P, Wielsøe M, Long M: **Assessment of chemical mixtures using biomarkers of combined biological activity: a screening study in human placentas.** *Reprod Toxicol* 2021, **100**:143–154.
51. Escher BI, Neale PA: **Effect-based trigger values for mixtures of chemicals in surface water detected with in vitro bioassays.** *Environ Toxicol Chem* 2021, **40**:487–499.
52. Neale PA, Escher BI, de Baat ML, Enault J, Leusch FD: **Effect-based trigger values are essential for the uptake of effect-based methods in water safety planning.** *Environ Toxicol Chem* 2023, **42**:714–726.
53. Escher BI, Lamoree M, Antignac J-P, Scholze M, Herzler M, Hamers T, Jensen TK, Audebert M, Busquet F, Maier D: **Mixture risk assessment of complex real-life mixtures—the PANORAMIX project.** *Int J Environ Res Publ Health* 2022, **19**:12990.
- The foundations and workplan of the PANORAMIX project are presented in this concept paper. An innovative way to perform chemical mixture risk assessment is proposed by integrating high-throughput whole-mixture-based in vitro strategies, chemical profiling and effect directed analysis.

54. Simon E, van Velzen M, Brandsma SH, Lie E, Loken K, de Boer J, Bytingsvik J, Jenssen BM, Aars J, Hamers T, Lamoree MH: **Effect-directed analysis to explore the polar bear exposome: identification of thyroid hormone disrupting compounds in plasma.** *Environ Sci Technol* 2013, **47**: 8902–8912.
55. Weiss JM, Andersson PL, Zhang J, Simon E, Leonards PE, Hamers T, Lamoree MH: **Tracing thyroid hormone-disrupting compounds: database compilation and structure-activity evaluation for an effect-directed analysis of sediment.** *Anal Bioanal Chem* 2015, **407**:5625–5634.
56. Ghisari M, Long M, Tabbo A, Bonefeld-Jorgensen EC: **Effects of currently used pesticides and their mixtures on the function of thyroid hormone and aryl hydrocarbon receptor in cell culture.** *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol* 2015, **284**:292–303.
57. Jonkers TJH, Meijer J, Vlaanderen JJ, Vermeulen RCH, Houtman CJ, Hamers T, Lamoree MH: **High-performance data processing workflow incorporating effect-directed analysis for feature prioritization in suspect and nontarget screening.** *Environ Sci Technol* 2022, **56**:1639–1651.
- Authors present for the first time a validated workflow that combines high throughput effect directed analysis with suspect and nontarget screening chemical profiling. This work sets the grounds for harmonized effect directed analysis approaches that will allow the identification of chemicals of concern in real-life complex mixtures.
58. Vinggaard AM, Bonefeld-Jorgensen EC, Jensen TK, Fernandez MF, Rosenmai AK, Taxvig C, Rodríguez-Carrillo A, Wielse M, Long M, Olea N, Antignac JP, Hamers T, Lamoree M: **Receptor-based in vitro activities to assess human exposure to chemical mixtures and related health impacts.** *Environ Int* 2021, **146**:106191.
- State-of-the-art review on the use of receptor-based in vitro assays to assess human exposure to chemical mixtures and related health impacts. The authors identify the need of novel approaches to use in chemical toxicity assessment.
59. Fernández MF, Rivas A, Olea-Serrano F, Cerrillo I, Molina-Molina JM, Araque P, Martínez-Vidal JL, Olea N: **Assessment of total effective xenoestrogen burden in adipose tissue and identification of chemicals responsible for the combined estrogenic effect.** *Anal Bioanal Chem* 2004, **379**: 163–170.